
APPROACHES, INNOVATIVE TOOLS – TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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ABSTRACT:

The paper aims to spotlight the best version of English Language Teaching Methods, Advanced Tools, Technologies, and Strategies. Business, Teaching, Medical, Law, Politics, Trading, Media, and Science–Technology spheres include the English language to exhibit ideas, state views, and communicate with suitable terminologies, vocabulary, and forms of sentences with meticulous structures and rules of language and grammar components. Hence, teaching the English language becomes and demands enormous prominence, as it serves to accumulate varieties of components in its own systematic contexts and expressions.

The English language is made up of a unique nature consisting of Symbol, Sound, and Sense, in literal terms known as Graphology, Phonology, and Semantics. Further, it contains Paragraphs, Sentences, Clauses, and much more. To execute verbal communication, Dialects, Diction, Vocabulary, Pronunciation, Phonetics, and Expressions are utilised. Besides, to present written/non-verbal communication components such as spellings, handwriting, grammar, punctuation, structure, and paragraph making are keenly observed. Phraseology for Phrases, Morphology for Words, and Orthography for Spellings are the studies which teach the entire major key factors of the English language. Since many of the in-depth mechanisms are inherited in this language, teaching with effective methods plays a major role; with the aid of advanced tools and technologies, the teaching and learning process develops a strong operative mode.

KEYWORDS:

Graphology, Phonology, Semantics, Morphology, Orthography,
Phraseology.

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The structure of the English language is baffling, yet still comprehensible. The merge of different languages, deriving terms from Latin, Greek, Indian, and American sources, and counting with Old English, Middle English, and appropriately connected with a West Germanic language with roots in Anglo-Saxon England is the unique identity of this language. The variety of the English language is one of the noticeable aspects, including British English and American English. The beauty of the language, from Geoffrey Chaucer, the first finder of the English language, to Grammarian Lindley Murray, the Father of English Grammar, has penned exceptional pieces of literature and components of English structure.

In the existing state, English Language Teaching is not limited to basic alphabets or classic Grammar; it has reached new heights with various kinds by including advanced tools and technologies. From classics to the contemporary era, the essence of the English Language and its Teaching Methodologies are remarkable. The legends of English Literature to Contemporary Writers have adopted their own way of writing skills, which assist in learning and teaching English teaching methodologies.

Few instances of Classic Texts/Quotes/Scenes and usage of Tools on English Language-Teaching

William Shakespeare – The Tempest (Play)

Caliban: “You taught me language and my profit on’t Is, I know how to curse. The red plague rid you For learning me your language!” (Act I, Scene 2).

The quote is not exclusive to the outburst of the exhausting notion of the character, but the conventional way of training and teaching skills of language has made the character significantly solid, which is witnessing how a non-native speaker has gained sufficient knowledge and grip on the language and is leading to pay back with a rigorous reaction using the learnt language.

George Bernard Shaw – Pygmalion (Play)

Prof. Henry Higgins, involved in a prominent research task on Phonetics. An ear-shaped recording tool/instrument demonstrates the usage of technical tools along with amplifying apparatus for listening to sounds, concealed microphones for speaking, and further equipment witnesses the development of tools and aids in early eras. Further, Prof. Henry Higgins, a Professor of Linguistics/Phonetician, bets to convert a garden Flower Girl to pass her off as a posh lady at the Ambassador's ball with refined English Language Skills and elite classy appearance.

Harry Hemsley – The English Language (Poem)

The poem brings out the importance of the English language and emphasizes more on the inexplicable peculiarities of the structure of this language.

‘Some words have different meanings,
And yet they’re spelt the same.
A cricket is an insect,
To play it-it’s a game.
On every hand, in every land,
it’s thoroughly agreed,
the English language to explain
is very hard indeed.....’

E.M. Forster, an English Author, quotes, “English literature is a flying fish,” which denotes that the literature of the English language possesses a versatile capability to transcend limitations and explore new realms. Hence, the concept of language teaching is

scripted in Classic Texts to Advanced Contemporary aids; each has its form, style, ways, and ideologies to execute the means of teaching.

Brief frameworks on – Teaching Components of English Language and its conventional Methods.

Literature

Prose, Parable, Epistle, Fable, Excerpts, Drama, Short Story/ Play, Threnody, Novel, Poem, Elegy, Biography, Autobiography, Verses, and more. The effective method of teaching the literature part of the English language contains Narration Skills, Recitation Skills, and Discoursing Strategies. The Lecturing Method works as a magical mode when themes, motifs, characters, outline summary, and conclusion are effectively delivered. Further, Translation, Direct, Structural, Communicative, Bilingual, Suggestopedia, Situational, and Reading methods and approaches bridge the connectivity of the teaching and learning process meticulously.

Translation Method: It has no systematic sense nor are any specific norms allotted. The prime focus is on the native language of the learner and the target language (English) used together; the teacher must be aware of both languages. Reading aloud is encouraged rather than spoken language.

Direct Method: It is noted as a monolingual method. A single language is used to conduct the class. Communication and thinking in the target language (English) take place. Motivating to interact in the target language allows for discussions.

Structural Approach: It is the teaching of the English language with a focus on selected structures. Oral tasks play a major role; the learner is taught structure by creating a conducive language learning atmosphere. Oral work offers suitable chances to progress in listening skills as well.

Bilingual Method: It includes two languages, i.e., the language to be learnt and the mother tongue. It is used to convey the entire

content of the topic in both languages. Accuracy and Fluency could be well taught; the sentence is the unit of teaching in this method.

Suggestopedia Approach: It is advocated by Dr. Georgi Lozanov, a Psychiatrist, to teach language. Suggest means ‘advice’ and ‘pedia’ means mainstreams. This methodology of teaching English is a humanistic approach; under Parapsychology, it bridges a gap between the conscious and unconscious mind. The motto is to learn the language in a joyful and relaxed way, which maintains cheerful competence.

Vocabulary Teaching: Perception, Recognition, Imitation, and Reproduction are the major four natural steps to master the skills. Conceptual meanings between words, Polysemy (various meanings for a single word according to context), chunks of language contents, and more could be taught through Quizzes, word building, word caterpillar, and scrabble activities that will remain beneficial. To teach Literature, setting up a Literature Club will support and promote the teaching ravishingly.

Communication Language Teaching (CLT)

Interview Skills, Soft Skills, Negotiation Skills, Corporate Communication Skills, Job Skills, and further professional Language Functions require well-versed training strategies and ICT-based LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing) Teaching Methods.

Audio-Visual Approach

Film Texts, TED Talks, Interview Clips, Motion Pictures.

To teach Communication Skills, introducing a Language Club makes teaching more live and experiential.

Teaching of Grammar

The science of sounds, inflexions, and constructions used in language and the set of rules followed to construct meaningful sentences is called grammar. Codifying and speeding up the language learning process is a key factor in teaching grammar. Functional and

Formal Grammar, a paramount part of the English language, includes two major methods which assist in teaching grammar concepts with accuracy.

- **Deductive Method:** Rules and definitions are given directly to memorise by the learners.
- **Inductive Method:** The learners explore to formulate a rule or definition with appropriate examples.

Teaching of Composition

Composing with words and sentences are the chief characteristics of composition. Language exercises such as Essays, Precis, Paraphrasing, Columns, Articles, Advertisements, Brochures, Blogs, Product Manuals, Business Correspondence, e-mail drafting, and further writing require the Chalk and Talk method and Presentation Skills to make teaching impactful.

Sky Ladder: The effective way of structuring the piece of writing, building up ideas and plans sequentially. The method is similar to climbing a ladder, where each step of the paragraph logically leads to the next.

Quadruple: It focuses on four major key aspects, which stand as a special feature of this method. Content, Structure, Language, and Style assist in organizing and developing well-supported arguments and expressing effectively in writing.

Cobweb Approach: This method starts with a central idea or theme; later, it explores related ideas that branch out from it, often returning to the same central idea. It allows building organic development and exploration of different facets of a topic.

Synectics: It leads towards generative thinking ability and promotes creativity among the learners. It is a creative problem-solving technique that uses metaphor and analogy to generate new ideas.

Conventional or traditional methods of teaching and learning

the English language with their own format, tools, and structure have been celebrated to date in classrooms. Further, to uplift the essence and introduce new technology and innovation in the sphere of English language teaching and learning, it has created its unique path and is welcomed with leveled-up creativity.

Some AI Tools and Technology for Literature, Language Components, Research Process

Chatbots, Google Translate, ELSA, and more are leading the domain of language with versatile technology and technical power, which assists in fetching all sorts of information and details of language learning aspects.

Software, Apps, Digital Platforms to teach and learn English Literature and Language Components

- www.pronunciation.com – Assists to learn sound, symbol, and pronunciation.
- Lanquill – Helps to learn the skills of LSRW with ample activities and tasks with a scoreboard and provides a certificate.
- Duolingo – Fun, gamified lessons covering vocabulary, grammar, listening & pronunciation.
- Babbel – Short, practical lessons focused on real-world conversation skills and pronunciation.

Best AI Tools for Language Components

- ELSA Speak, Speechling, Forvo, YouGlish for Phonetics and Phonology.
- Quizlet, Anki, Vocabulary.com for Morphology.
- Grammarly, NoRedInk, British Council Grammar for Syntax.
- Linguee, Reverso Context, WordReference for Semantics.
- TypingClub, Oxford Dictionary, Grammarly for Orthography.
- FluentU, BBC Learning English, AI Chatbots for Pragmatics.

AI Platforms for Research Process

- Zotero and Mendeley – Provide suitable templates.
- Jenni AI – Refers to appropriate headings and formats.
- Elicit – Generates relevant content writing.
- StealthWriter – Gives a human touch to the content and provides English assistance.
- Graphviz, Data Studio, and Kaggle – Shapes, diagrams, graphs, and charts.

The endorsement of AI in the usage of the English language with the best features is transforming and reaching the zenith. The personalised learning space, assistance in writing and correcting grammar contents, self-practice on pronunciation and speaking, supporting translation tasks, supervising content creation, and further facilitation are playing a vital role in the English language teaching and learning process.

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